

Information Literacy Skills and Electronic Resources Usage by Lecturers in Federal Universities in North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: This study investigates information literacy skills (ILS) as a predictor of e-resource use by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central region of Nigeria.

Methodology: A correlational descriptive survey was conducted among 5,185 lecturers from seven federal universities in Nigeria's North-central region. A stratified random sampling selected 60% of departments, and a disproportionate stratified sampling chose 1,065 lecturers (five per department). Data collection used adapted ILS and E-resource scales. Reliability tests showed Cronbach's alpha of 0.81 and $r = 0.84$ for E-resource use, indicating good reliability. Data analysis included descriptive and inferential statistics, revealing a moderate level (2.61) of information literacy skills among lecturers, above the threshold of 2.50.

Findings: The primary purpose of e-resources use is to enhance research work by accessing relevant information from other disciplines, while the most frequently used e-resources were social networking sites (42.7%). A significant positive relationship ($r = 0.120^*$; $df = 1,020$; $P < 0.05$) exists between information literacy skills and e-resources use among lecturers in federal universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Conclusion: Lecturers' use of electronic information resources depends on their information literacy skills. Universities should provide access to e-resources and evaluate faculty development programs to improve these skills for better research and teaching.

Study Type: Empirical study

Keywords: Electronic Information Resources Use, Information Literacy Skills, Lecturers in Federal Universities, North-central, Nigeria.

Introduction

Modern society is driven by information and communication technologies, which enable easier access to information from anywhere, regardless of geographical location. Consequently, university managements utilise information and communication technologies to retrieve information needed by lecturers for teaching and research. Due to the abundance of information resources and various methods of obtaining needed information, lecturers are expected to be well-equipped with adequate information skills to find, locate, retrieve, evaluate, and use information for study and research. Poor skills could lead to unethical use of information, which is often available in an unfiltered form. The vast amount of information and its suspicious nature in the public domain demand that lecturers acquire suitable information literacy skills for finding, evaluating, and obtaining information from e-resources for academic purposes. Essentially, lecturers need to determine the reliability and authenticity of electronic information resources that may be required for their research work.

These resources are primarily stored electronically and accessible through computer systems and networks. They consist of high-quality information generated by scholars across various disciplines of human knowledge and serve as an alternative to print resources. These include

books, e-journals, e-theses and dissertations, the online public access catalogue (OPAC), institutional repositories, social networking sites, and more. They are also available in full-text articles, journals, books, databases, photographs, images, music, pictures, and other multimedia formats. These resources enable access to information that might be restricted to users due to geographical limitations. According to Jestin and Sorman (2016), they are less expensive, more informative, useful, and time-saving compared to traditional print sources.

In today's information age, the use of e-resources is invaluable to lecturers, providing quick access to relevant information that can help them enrich their teaching and research with new ideas and innovations as often as possible. Historically, it has been observed that university libraries serve as common grounds where the entire community can access e-resources that may support the university's mission but are often too costly for the average lecturer to afford. However, studies have shown that a significant portion of lecturers still lack the skills to effectively navigate information spaces for their professional development. As a result, e-resources remain largely underutilised due to insufficient training on how to harness them for study and research. Therefore, a lack or low level of information literacy skills (ILS) could pose a major obstacle to the effective use of e-resources for career advancement. This study, therefore, investigates information literacy skills as a predictor of e-resources use by lecturers in federal universities in North-central Nigeria.

Research questions

1. What is the level of information literacy skills among lecturers in federal universities in North-Central Nigeria?
2. What is the purpose of using e-resources for lecturers in federal universities in North-central Nigeria?
3. What is the frequency of e-resource use by lecturers in federal universities in North-central Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₀1 There is no significant relationship between information literacy skills and the use of e-resources by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central region of Nigeria.

Literature Review

Ubogu (2021) investigated the challenges faced by academic staff when accessing electronic databases at Delta State University Library in Abraka. Using a survey method and questionnaires, the study collected data from academic staff. It found that respondents utilise HINARI, AJOL, EBSCO Host, JSTOR, and AGORA for their research. However, the findings also indicated that a lack of user education and guidance hampers effective use of e-resources. To address this, the study recommends implementing training programmes to improve e-resource utilisation.

Odunewu and Aluko-Arowolo (2018) investigated computer competence and the use of electronic resources by Olabisi Onabanjo faculty members. The questionnaire was the main data collection tool used to obtain information from the respondents. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics. The major finding indicated that faculty members with adequate information skills could retrieve valuable information from electronic resources for teaching and research. Abubakar and Akor (2017) investigated the use of databases and research productivity among agricultural scientists in federal universities in the North Central region of Nigeria. Questionnaires and documentary records were the primary data collection instruments used to gather information from the respondents. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The major findings highlighted inadequate information skills, slow

internet services, and high bandwidth costs as obstacles to using e-resources among agricultural scientists.

Using a descriptive survey research design, Agboola, Okorie, Omotoso, Bamigboye, and Bello (2018) examined the use of electronic information resources and the research output of academic staff in Colleges of Agriculture at a Nigerian university. The questionnaire was the primary data collection instrument used to gather information from the respondents. The findings indicated that slow download speeds and inadequate search strategies were major constraints to the use of e-resources for research among the academic staff. Kalbande, Shinde, and Igle (2013) studied the use of electronic resources by faculty members at Mahatma Phule Agricultural University, India. The questionnaire was the main tool employed to collect information from the respondents. Data analysis was presented in the form of frequencies and percentages. The main findings highlighted limited internet access and a lack of training and time as key constraints to retrieving information from electronic resources among the respondents.

Kalbande and Chavan (2018) studied the use of digital library resources by lecturers in engineering colleges at the University of Pune. Data analysis was presented in the form of frequency counts and percentages. Main findings identified poor internet connectivity and lack of training as barriers to accessing information from electronic resources among the respondents. Kumari and Mallaiah (2017) assessed the digital information literacy skills of faculty members at a college in Mangalore. A questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument to gather information from the respondents. Data analysis was based on frequency counts and percentages. The main outcome revealed that respondents were able to obtain information from the internet for study and research.

Methodology

The descriptive survey of the correlation type was used for the study. The population comprised all 5,185 lecturers in the seven federal universities located in North-Central Nigeria. The zone consists of six states: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau states, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). A two-stage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, 60% of all departments were selected using stratified random sampling. There are 354 departments across all federal universities in North-Central Nigeria. Consequently, 213 departments were randomly chosen, representing roughly 60% of all departments within each university. The second stage involved randomly selecting lecturers from the chosen departments using the disproportionate stratified random sampling technique; this resulted in a total sample size of 1065 lecturers for the study. The researcher adapted the Information Literacy Skills Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Kurbanoglu Akkoyunlu and Umay (2006) and also adopted the e-resources use scale developed by Singh (2013) for data collection. The information literacy skills scale was presented to experts for face and content validity. Cronbach's Alpha was used to validate the instrument, obtaining a value of $\alpha=0.81$, while the reliability coefficient for the e-resources use scale was $r=0.84$. These values were sufficiently high to consider the instruments reliable. Data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were utilised to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis were employed to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and discussion

A total of 1,065 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents at various universities. However, 1,021 copies were properly completed and usable, resulting in a response rate of 95.9%.

Research question one: What is the level of information literacy skills among lecturers in federal universities in North-Central Nigeria?

Tables 1a and 1b present the information literacy skills of lecturers at federal universities in the North-central region of Nigeria.

Table 1a Information literacy skills of lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria

S/N	Recognise information needs skills, I:	SD		D		A		SA		Me an (\bar{x})	Std .
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1	understand the need to use information resources to undertake research.	19	19.	26	26.	23	22.	32	32.	2.6	1.1
		6	2	8	2	0	5	7	0	7	16
2	recognise a need for information and data to achieve a specific end.	22	21.	11	11.	29	28.	39	38.	2.8	1.1
		0	5	9	7	2	6	0	2	3	55
3	cannot define my specific information resources needs.	30	29.	46	45.	13	12.	11	11.	2.0	.94
		4	8	6	6	2	9	9	7	6	3
4	rely on students to search for required information resources for my research.	34	33.	29	29.	24	24.	13	13.	2.1	1.0
		0	3	9	3	5	0	7	4	8	39
5	define my research topic using simple keywords	13	12.	73	7.1	40	39.	41	40.	3.0	.99
		2	9			3	5	3	5	7	4
6	am able to manage time effectively when using information sources.	14	14.	13	13.	41	40.	32	31.	2.8	1.0
		6	3	9	6	6	7	0	3	9	05
	Weighted mean									(\bar{x} = 2.62)	
	Information seeking strategies skills, I:										
7	understand search techniques available to find information resources that are relevant to my research tasks	13	13.	21	21.	47	46.	19	19.	2.7	.92
		7	4	5	1	5	5	4	0	1	4
8	have low understanding of the web as complex mix of free and fee based materials	34	34.	41	40.	13	13.	12	12.	2.0	.98
		7	0	2	4	7	4	5	2	4	1
9	can initiate search strategies by using keywords and Boolean logic	19	19.	19	19.	47	46.	15	15.	2.5	.96
		6	2	4	0	5	5	6	3	8	7
10	don't use controlled vocabulary specific to my discipline	35	34.	41	40.	13	13.	12	12.	2.0	.98
		1	4	1	3	4	1	5	2	3	2
11	can limit search strategies by subject, language and date	13	13.	19	19.	27	27.	40	40.	2.9	1.0
		7	4	6	2	9	3	9	1	4	62
	Weighted mean									(\bar{x} = 2.46)	
	Locate and access skills, I:										
12	have understanding of how my university library provide access to information resources	13	12.	28	27.	35	34.	26	25.	2.7	.98
		1	8	0	4	0	3	0	5	2	3
13	do not understand the risks associated with using free internet resources for my research	42	41.	27	26.	13	13.	19	19.	2.1	1.1
		0	1	1	5	4	1	6	2	0	41
14	know appropriate techniques to collect current information for my research	23	23.	73	7.1	41	40.	29	28.	2.7	1.1
		8	3			6	7	4	8	5	09
15	am able to *identify when available resources have not met my information need	10	10.	19	19.	32	32.	39	38.	2.9	.99
		4	2	8	4	8	1	1	3	9	3
16	lack knowledge of data management software and techniques to manage data	17	17.	33	33.	34	34.	15	15.	2.4	.95
		8	4	7	0	9	2	7	4	8	2

17	do not have knowledge to keep information for future use	17	17.	15	15.	24	23.	44	43.	2.9	1.1
		6	2	7	4	3	8	5	6	4	30
18	use approved passwords for access to information resources I need for my research	19	19.	13	13.	21	21.	47	46.	2.9	1.1
		8	4	3	0	8	4	2	2	4	69
	Weighted mean									($\bar{x} = 2.70$)	
	Use of information skills, I:										
19	understand intellectual property, copyright, and fair use of copyrighted materials	19	19.	84	8.2	34	34.	39	38.	2.9	1.1
		4	0			9	2	4	6	2	06
20	do comply with university policies on access to information resources	31	30.	16	16.	32	32.	21	21.	2.4	1.1
		1	5	3	0	9	2	8	4	4	33
21	am able to select resources which 'best fit' my research task	19	19.	73	7.1	19	19.	55	54.	3.1	1.1
		4	0			6	2	8	7	0	71
22	cannot identify different formats in which information may be stored for future use in my research.	39	38.	29	29.	19	19.	13	13.	2.0	1.0
		0	2	6	0	8	4	7	4	8	52
23	find it less cumbersome to identify issues related to privacy and security in both the print and electronic environments	81	7.9	21	21.	22	22.	49	48.	3.1	1.0
				8	4	6	1	6	6	1	02
24	demonstrate awareness of issues relating to the rights of others including ethics, data protection, copyright, plagiarism and any other intellectual property issues	13	13.	15	15.	47	46.	25	25.	2.8	.95
		5	2	7	4	3	3	6	1	3	2
25	have low understanding of issues surrounding copyright and plagiarism in research	43	42.	34	34.	19	19.	40	3.9	1.8	.86
		5	6	8	1	8	4			5	8
26	find it difficult to preserve the integrity of information resources and computer facilities	30	29.	54	53.	93	9.1	81	7.9	1.9	.83
		3	7	4	3					5	9
	Weighted mean									($\bar{x} = 2.54$)	
	Synthesis skills, I:										
27	understand that existing information can be combined with original thought, experiment and analysis to produce new information	81	7.9	18	18.	48	47.	27	26.	2.9	.87
				6	2	3	3	1	5	2	2
28	do not lack the needed skill to create new knowledge in my research work	12	11.	24	24.	41	40.	23	23.	2.7	.94
		1	9	6	1	6	7	8	3	6	3
29	can synthesise newly gathered information with previous information	11	11.	22	22.	28	27.	39	39.	2.9	1.0
		4	2	7	2	2	6	8	0	4	28
30	have low ability to reflect on problems I encountered	43	42.	26	25.	21	21.	11	11.	2.0	1.0
		0	1	0	5	8	4	3	1	1	38

Table 1a Information literacy skills of lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria (Cont'd)

	Synthesis skills, I:	SD		D		A		SA		Me an (\bar{x})	Std .
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
31	cannot use computer and other technologies for studying interaction of ideas and other phenomena	34	33.	31	31.	23	22.	12	12.	2.1	1.0
		6	9	7	0	2	7	6	3	4	21
32	can determine the content and form the parts of both my written and oral presentation (introduction, statement of problem, conclusion)	79	7.7	10	10.	41	40.	42	41.	3.1	.89
				4	2	2	4	6	7	6	6
	Weighted mean									($\bar{x} = 2.66$)	
	Evaluative skills, I:										

33	understand issues of quality, accuracy, relevance, bias reputation and credibility relating to information and data sources found for my research	25 2	24. 7	11 2	11. 0	39 4	38. 6	26 3	25. 8	2.6 5	1.1 12
34	my understanding of concept of accuracy, relevance and comprehensiveness of information resources is relatively low.	37 9	37. 1	45 7	44. 8	11 4	11. 2	71	7.0	1.8 8	.86 4
35	can choose range of materials on topics, taking into account currency, bias, authority, accuracy, relevance and comprehensiveness	12 5	12. 2	17 8	17. 4	37 3	36. 5	34 5	33. 8	2.9 2	.99 8
36	have ability distinguish different information sources and the information they provide	18 7	18. 3	19 5	19. 1	28 9	28. 3	35 0	34. 3	2.7 9	1.1 05
37	lack the ability to read, analyse and select main ideas from information resources found for my research	28 4	27. 8	30 2	29. 6	24 1	23. 6	19 4	19. 0	2.3 4	1.0 78
Weighted mean		($\bar{x} = 2.52$)									
Communicative skills, I:											
38	understand that data can be presented in different ways	40	3.9	17 0	16. 7	46 1	45. 2	35 0	34. 3	3.1 0	.81 1
39	find it difficult to create bibliographic records and organise the bibliography for my research	28 5	27. 9	53 0	51. 9	81	7.9	12 5	12. 2	2.0 5	.92 0
40	am able to cite bibliographic references in research reports.	73	7.1	17 4	17. 0	23 8	23. 3	53 6	52. 5	3.2 1	.96 8
41	can select appropriate publications and dissemination outlets in which to publish	84	8.2	73 7.1	7.1	47 4	46. 4	39 0	38. 2	3.1 5	.87 3
42	can communicate effectively using appropriate publication channels	11 7	11. 5	13 7	13. 4	33 8	33. 1	42 9	42. 0	3.0 6	1.0 05
43	cannot communicate my research effectively and verbally	21 8	21. 4	56 4	55. 2	16 5	16. 2	74	7.2	2.0 9	.81 1
Weighted mean		($\bar{x} = 2.78$)									
n = 1021; Overall Mean ($\bar{x} = 112.38$)											

Table 1a presents the response rate on information literacy skills of lecturers in federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria. The results in Table 1a show that lecturers in these federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria demonstrated a moderate level of information literacy skills: proficiency in information recognition, information seeking strategies, location and access to information, information synthesis, evaluation, communication, and use of information.

By extending this analysis to capture the subscales analysis of information literacy skills, the findings further revealed that the most significant sub-scale is communicative skills. ($\bar{x}=2.78$); followed by the locate and access skill ($\bar{x}=2.70$); synthesis skill ($\bar{x}=2.66$); recognise information skills ($\bar{x}=2.62$); use of information skills ($\bar{x}=2.54$); evaluative skill($\bar{x}=2.52$); and information-seeking strategies skill ($\bar{x}=2.46$).

Table 1b: Level of information literacy skills of the lecturers

Variable	No of items	Likert points	Level scale	Overall mean (\bar{x})	Decision
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Information literacy skills	43	4	58 – 114	112.38	Moderate
			115 – 172		

A test of norms was conducted to assess the level of information literacy skills among lecturers. Results in Table 1b indicate that the overall mean () for the lecturers' information literacy skills falls within the scale of "58-114". The norm scale: "1-57" signifies a low literacy level, "58-114" is considered moderate, while "115-172" is high. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of lecturers' information literacy skills in federal universities in North-central Nigeria is moderate. This finding aligns with that of Vikramjeet, Parmar, and Rao (2023), who examined information literacy skills among faculty members and research scholars at Central Sanskrit University, Vedavyas Campus, Balahar, and found that respondents possessed sufficient information literacy skills to meet their basic research needs, with a considerable number attending library orientation programmes. Similarly, this study's results support the findings of Chanchinmawia, Verma, and Soni (2019), who studied faculty members' information literacy skills at Mizoram University and reported that the majority demonstrated appropriate information skills necessary for retrieving information for their research work.

Research question two: What is the purpose of electronic resources use by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria?

Table 2: Purpose of e-resources use to lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria

S/N	Purposes of using e-resources:	SD		D		A		SA		Mea n (\bar{x})	Std.
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1	Obtain information for my professional training development (conferences & workshops)	12 6	12. 3	13 7	13. 4	258	25. 3	50 0	49. 0	3.11	1.05 2
2	Teaching my students irrespective of their levels	78	7.6	16 5	16. 2	417	40. 8	36 1	35. 4	3.04	.906
3	Update my knowledge in my discipline	12 6	12. 3	16 5	16. 2	413	40. 5	31 7	31. 0	2.90	.978
4	Enrich my research with relevant information from other disciplines	81	7.9	64	6.3	271	26. 5	60 5	59. 3	3.37	.914
5	For my research work	17 4	17. 0	17 5	17. 1	414	40. 5	25 8	25. 3	2.74	1.02 0
6	Materials for course delivery	53	5.2	15 7	15. 4	392	38. 4	41 9	41. 0	3.15	.866
7	Obtain information for my personal needs and development	10 4	10. 2	20 2	19. 8	360	35. 3	35 5	34. 8	2.95	.975

8	Know the current state of research in my discipline	186	18.2	81	7.9	230	22.5	524	51.3	3.07	1.148
9	Obtain information from blog discussions on subject areas related to my discipline	178	17.4	60	5.9	218	21.4	565	55.3	3.15	1.136

n = 1021

Response rates of electronic resource use are presented in Table 2. The majority of the respondents indicated that they obtained information from electronic resources to enrich their research with relevant information from other disciplines ($\bar{x}=3.37$). In the same vein, most of the respondents affirmed the use of e-resources to complement materials for course delivery ($\bar{x}=3.15$). Similarly, the majority of the respondents indicated that they obtain information from blog discussions on subject areas related to their discipline from e-resources ($\bar{x}=3.15$). Thus, most of the respondents indicated they used electronic resources to enhance the quality of their research work ($\bar{x}=2.74$). Therefore, it can be deduced that lecturers in federal universities in the North-central region of Nigeria rely on electronic resources to enrich their research work with relevant information from other disciplines, obtain information from blog discussions on related subject areas, and stay informed about the current state of research in their discipline. The current finding aligns with the study by Ifijeh, Ogbomo, and Ifijeh (2018), who examined the use of library resources and research productivity among lecturers in private universities in the South-South region of Nigeria. The study reported that the majority of lecturers consistently published research reports/monographs and journal articles.

Research question three: How frequently are electronic resources used by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria?

Table 3: Frequency of electronic resources use by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria

S/N	How often do you use the under listed e-resources	Not at all		Occasionally		Weekly/once a week		2-3 times a week		Daily		Mean (\bar{x})	Std.
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
1	E-books	218	21.4	84	8.2	114	11.2	215	21.1	39	38.2	3.47	1.569
2	E-journals	74	7.2	217	21.3	81	7.9	518	50.7	13	12.8	3.41	1.166
3	Open access databases	123	12.0	144	14.1	74	7.2	640	62.7	40	3.9	3.32	1.142
4	OPAC	331	32.4	327	32.0	132	12.9	178	17.4	53	5.2	2.31	1.234
5	E-theses and dissertation	74	7.2	51	5.0	144	14.1	556	54.5	19	19.2	3.73	1.056
6	E-courseware	478	46.8	309	30.3	20	2.0	20	2.0	19	19.0	2.16	1.501
7	E-reference materials	379	37.1	363	35.6	98	9.6	117	11.5	64	6.3	2.14	1.213
8	Institutional repositories	218	21.4	194	19.0	411	40.3	145	14.2	53	5.2	2.63	1.121

9	E-newspapers/magazines	116	11.4	162	15.9	112	11.0	552	54.1	79	7.7	3.31	1.170
10	E-conference papers	64	6.3	240	23.5	301	29.5	265	26.0	15	14.8	3.19	1.140
11	E-preprints	258	25.3	384	37.6	61	6.0	254	24.9	64	6.3	2.49	1.277
12	E-maps	20	2.0	215	21.1	685	67.1	20	2.0	81	7.9	2.93	.788
13	E-patents/standards	137	13.4	525	51.4	114	11.2	117	11.5	12	12.5	2.58	1.222
14	Library websites	196	19.2	517	50.6	126	12.3	162	15.9	20	2.0	2.31	1.016
15	Open (free access resources)	53	5.2	117	11.5	243	23.8	426	41.7	18	17.8	3.56	1.070
16	Subscribed e-databases	385	37.7	321	31.4	125	12.2	73	7.1	11	11.5	2.23	1.328
17	Social networking sites	61	6.0	124	12.1	126	12.3	274	26.8	43	42.7	3.88	1.250
18	Cloud computing sites	512	50.1	185	18.1	148	14.5	123	12.0	53	5.2	2.04	1.263
19	Anti-plagiarism software	206	20.2	482	47.2	143	14.0	53	5.2	13	13.4	2.44	1.249

n = 1021

Table 3 presents the response rate on the frequency of e-resource use by lecturers in federal universities in the North Central, Nigeria. The findings revealed that the most frequently used e-resources are social networking sites (42.7%), e-books(38.2%),e-theses and dissertations (19.2%), e-courseware (19.0%), open (free access resources) (17.8%), e-journals (12.8%), and open access databases (3.32%), respectively. While the least used e-resources include: library websites (50.6%), e-patent/standards (51.4%), e-reference materials (35.6%), e-preprints (37.6%), and subscribed e-databases (31.4%).

The result of this study aligns with that of Oladeji and Adeyeye (2022) regarding electronic information resources use and research productivity of lecturers in private universities in Oyo State. It suggests that most respondents frequently used electronic reference sources, online public access catalogues, and offline databases, while the least used databases included social media platforms and CD-ROMS.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between information literacy skills and e-resources use by lecturers in federal universities in the North-central, Nigeria.

Table 4: Relationship between information literacy skills and electronic resources use by the lecturers using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Analysis

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	Df	Sig. (p)
Information literacy skills	112.38	8.100	1,021			

E-resources use	54.14	8.839	1,021	.120**	1,020	.000
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*. Significant at 0.05 level

A brief review of Table 4 indicates that there is a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.120^{**}$; $df = 1,020$; $P < 0.05$) between information literacy skills and the use of electronic resources by lecturers in federal universities in North-central Nigeria. This suggests that the higher the lecturers' level of information literacy skills, the more likely they are to access timely, reliable, and relevant information for their scholarly publications. Consequently, the hypothesis is rejected.

The finding aligns with the position of Odunewu and Aluko-Arowolo (2018), who investigated computer competence and electronic resources use by Olabisi Onabanjo faculty members. They found that most faculty members demonstrated adequate information literacy skills and could retrieve useful information from e-resources for teaching and research. This study's findings support the submission of Ajayi, Haliso and Unegbu (2023), who examined the influence of information literacy skills on (EIRs) use by lecturers in private universities in South-West, Nigeria, and discovered that information literacy skills positively and significantly influence EIRs use by lecturers in South-West Nigeria.

Conclusion

Information literacy skills influence how lecturers utilise electronic information resources. In today's digital age, the use of electronic resources is crucial for lecturers, providing quick access to relevant information that can enhance their teaching and research with new ideas and innovations frequently. Historically, university libraries have served as a common platform for the community to access these e-resources, which support the university's mission but are often too costly for an average lecturer to afford. These resources are stored across various electronic databases on the internet, requiring lecturers to have specific skills to access and utilise them effectively. Only lecturers possessing appropriate information literacy skills are able to recognise their information needs, locate, evaluate, use, and communicate information in suitable formats tailored to their audience.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made based on the findings of the study:

Universities should enhance access to e-resources, including online databases, digital libraries, and academic databases. Offering faculty comprehensive access supports more effective and informed research and teaching.

Collaborating with industry partners and organisations specialising in information literacy to organise training sessions can improve faculties' skills in this area. Experts from these fields can share valuable insights into best practices and real-world applications.

University management should promote mentorship to support junior faculty in developing information literacy and utilising electronic resources. This guidance can facilitate the sharing of knowledge and best practices among faculty members.

Universities should establish evaluation and assessment systems to measure the effectiveness of faculty development programs in enhancing information literacy skills and the utilisation of e-resources.

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